
Valorisation and Curation of the ESA ERS Missions

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The European Remote Sensing satellite (ERS-1), launched more than 30 years ago, was one of the most sophisticated spacecrafts ever developed and launched by Europe, covering the monitoring of atmosphere, land, ocean and ice. Shortly after the launch of ERS-2 four years later, ESA decided to link the two satellites in the first 'tandem' mission which lasted for nine months. During this time the increased frequency and level of data available to scientists offered a unique opportunity to observe changes over a very short space of time. These pioneering missions have provided the basis for the remote sensing we have come to rely upon today to unravel the complexities of the way Earth works. The success of the ERS missions has helped Europe to gain clear leadership in several critical technologies and in the scientific use of Earth observation. The ERS missions have provided a stream of data which has changed our view of the world in which we live. It has provided us with new insights on our planet, the chemistry of our atmosphere, the behaviour of our oceans, and the effects of mankind's activity on our environment – creating new opportunities for scientific research and applications. During their lifetime, ERS data supported over 5000 projects producing some 4000 scientific publications. Archived data, which remain accessible, continue to provide us with a wealth of information and are continuously improved in the frame of ESA's Heritage Space Programme to build long-time data series with successor missions including Envisat and the Copernicus Sentinels.

The paper describes the full process of ERS missions valorisation and curation activities. ERS missions data are in fact continually reprocessed to align format with newer missions data, to exploit more recent algorithms, and to improve their quality and accuracy, with the ultimate goal to offer valuable long-term references in a wide range of fields. Reprocessing activities are also triggered by the availability of additional data recovered through transcription of heritage media containing unique data to fill identified gaps, or after repatriation to ESA of unique data acquired in the past by National or Foreign stations.

Beside these reprocessing activities, ad-hoc projects for the generation of Fundamental Data Records of data aligned with newer missions and addressing the generation of new products are ongoing. The Fundamental Data Records for Altimetry (FDR4ALT) project for example is generating innovative Earth system data records, called Fundamental Data Records (basically level 1 altimeter and radiometer data) and Thematic Data Records (basically level 2P geophysical products). The goal is to serve the different communities involved in long-term data exploitation over the different Earth surfaces: ocean, coastal, inland water, ice sheets, sea ice and atmosphere.

Introduction

The Heritage Space Programme responds to the mandate of preserving, making accessible, and valorising ESA heritage space data and associated information holdings generated by payloads and instruments on-board space platforms from ESA and ESA-managed Third Party Missions with a strong focus on their accessibility and exploitability. Over 40 Earth Observation missions (including ERS-1 and ERS-2) and 80 EO campaigns are currently included in the Heritage Space programme.

The ERS Programme has provided a stream of data which has changed our view of the world in which we live. It has provided us with new insights on our planet, the chemistry of our atmosphere, the behavior of our oceans, and the effects of mankind's activity on our environment – creating new opportunities for scientific research and applications.

The success of ERS also paved the way for further Earth Observation missions such as Envisat and today's Copernicus Sentinel family of satellites, which evolved on ESA's heritage systems developed and launched onboard ERS-1 and ERS-2. Together, these three generations of missions provide a record of 30+ years of continuous observations of our Planet, supplying valuable long-term datasets for research and operational applications benefitting from long time-series analysis.

ERS Programme

The ERS programme was composed of two missions, ERS-1 and ERS-2, which were launched into the same orbit in 1991 and 1995 respectively. The two spacecraft were designed as identical twins with one important difference – ERS-2 included an extra instrument (GOME) designed to monitor ozone levels in the atmosphere.

Due to the satellites' shared orbit, a tandem mission was implemented following the launch of ERS-2, whereby ERS-2 passed the same point on the ground one day later than ERS-1. The 'ERS tandem mission' doubled the number of measurement points for the radar altimeter and, more importantly laid the basis for an accurate, three-dimensional digital map of Earth's land surfaces, which for some of Earth's regions would have been impossible.

Following nine years of excellent service, over three times its planned lifetime, the ERS-1 mission ended on 10 March 2000 due to a failure in the on board attitude control system. Since its launch on 17 July 1991 ERS-1 made 45,000 orbits, acquiring more than 1.5 million individual Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) scenes. The ERS-2 satellite followed its predecessor's example greatly exceeding its three year life span with 16 years of successful operations. The satellite was safely taken out of service on 5 September 2011, due to low levels of remaining fuel. From when it was launched on 21 April 1995, ERS-2 made 85,000 orbits, travelling 3.5 billion km.

Figure 1 – ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites

Figure 2 – ERS-1 First Image and ERS-2 Last Image

ERS Instruments

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)

The SAR provides cloud-free radar images of mainly the Earth's surfaces, monitoring vegetation and growth, flooding, cultivation of land. It has also applications on the oceans and, through the interferometric SAR (InSAR) technique, can derive elevation models or detect small surface movements, of the order of a centimetres.

Wind Scatterometer (SCAT)

This instrument (together with the SAR forming the Active Microwave Instrument, AMI) maps the wind speed and wind direction over ocean surfaces.

Radar Altimeter (RA)

The Radar Altimeter is a nadir looking instrument sending radar signals to the earth and ocean surface to derive information on the wave height and wind speed (over oceans), the surface backscatter, and the height of the satellite above the surface.

Along-Track Scanning Radiometer (ATSR) and Microwave Sounder (MWR)

A sweeping mirror detects and maps infrared radiation in various wavelengths along the satellite track. When the sky is cloud-free, these measurements can be converted to land and sea surface temperature. Operating together with the ATSR, the Microwave Sounder provides a measurement of the total water vapour content in the Earth's atmosphere vertically below the satellite orbit.

Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment (GOME)

The GOME instrument on ERS-2 allows to map the ozone content in the upper atmosphere.

Precise Range and Range-Rate Equipment (PRARE) and Laser Retro-Reflector (LRR)

PRARE is an active satellite tracking equipment, whilst the Laser Retro-Reflector is purely passive.

Figure 3 – ERS-1 Instruments

ERS Ground Segment

The ERS programme was designed to serve a large variety of users with a comprehensive range of products and services.

Figure 4 – ERS Ground Segment

The characteristics of the ERS space segment in terms of its multi-sensor payload, orbit configurations and power requirements, imposed the implementation of a network of ground stations around the world to acquire the high bit rate SAR data (for which only direct readout was possible). In addition, facilities

had to be provided to permit the downloading, once per orbit, of the on-board recorded low bit rate (LBR) data. The instrument data was sent to Processing and Archiving Facilities (PAFs) for archiving and off-line product generation and delivery to users. The user interface and exploitation of the payload data was implemented at ESRIN by the Earthnet Programme Office (EPO); while the satellite planning and control functions, including the control of the Kiruna station were under the responsibility of ESOC in Darmstadt, Germany.

ERS missions Achievements (few examples)

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published reports that detailed the intensifying impacts of climate change, including melting of the ice sheets, sea level rise, ocean warming and acidification. Observations from ERS and Envisat have proven critical for monitoring changes to the ice sheets, which together with glacier mass loss, are now the dominant contributors to global sea level rise. Picture: Upsala Glacier

ERS and Envisat provided high-quality information on the annual formation and recovery of the Antarctic ozone hole, as well as the health of the ozone layer blanketing the rest of the planet, from the mid-1990s until 2012. Data from the heritage missions have proven to be a vital resource, helping the international community to track the impacts of the Montreal Protocol. Picture: Antarctic ozone hole

Missions such ERS-1 pioneered datasets on Earth’s surface using microwave, infrared and visible spectrum-based environmental monitoring and a comprehensive payload with several instruments including SAR and radar altimeter. Historically ERS datasets were called upon to monitor environmental and natural disasters such as flooding and earthquakes. However, to this day the ERS data acquired for some 20 years still provide invaluable land monitoring information and are continuously improved to build long time data series with newer missions.

Comparison of data from three generations of radar missions – Seasat, ERS and Sentinel-1 has shown the retreat of two large glaciers in southeast Greenland over a 36-year period. This analysis shows that the effects of climate change on the world’s second largest ice sheet have had a major impact over the past three decades. The glaciers show significant retreat, with the upper glacier receding by about 5.5 km over the past 36 years. This melt is contributing to sea-level rise and the release of more freshwater into the North Atlantic. Picture: Greenland glaciers retreat

ERS Preservation and Valorisation Effort

The Heritage Space Programme is since several years the ESA programmatic element ensuring the preservation and valorisation of the ERS missions data establishing and increasing the value of “preserved data sets” over their lifecycle, favouring their exploitation, possibly through the combination with other data records, and extending the communities using the data sets. Figure 5 shows the steps performed to preserve and valorise ERS missions data in alignment with the CEOS internationally recognised Best Practices [1].

Figure 5 – Preservation and Valorisation Workflow

Assessment and Objectives

The first step consisted in the compilation of an **appraisal questionnaire/survey** to assess mission assets and interest from the user communities and to gather an initial conception of what level of data preservation, accessibility and usability had to be ensured for the missions data in the long term. A self-assessment based on the use of a **Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix (DMSMM)** [2] was then performed to measure the overall status of preservation and curation of the mission. The matrix was then used to fix targets and define the activities to be implemented to preserve and improve the ERS missions data quality, accessibility, and usability.

DISCOVERABILITY	ACCESSIBILITY		USABILITY				PRESERVATION			CURATION		
	EMRP Metadata for Discovery	EMRP Online Access	EMRP Data Coding	EMRP Data Documentation	EMRP Data Traceability	EMRP Data Validation	EMRP Data Uncertainty	EMRP Data Quality Control	EMRP Data Preservation	EMRP Data Verification	EMRP Data Processing/Reprocessing	EMRP2 Performance & Resolvable Identifiers
Level 0 Not Managed	1) No catalog available 2) No advertising available	Data and metadata are not accessible online	1) Data Not Structured 2) No standard or proprietary data format or widely documented standard file format.	Partial and incomplete mission documentation	Limited product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness: No validation 2) Reference Data Quality: No validation 3) Reference Data: No validation 4) Validation Results: No validation	1) Uncertainty Method: Uncertainty characterization not performed, or method not documented 2) Uncertainty Sources: Uncertainty characterization not performed, or sources not documented 3) Uncertainty Values: No uncertainty information provided.	1) No control and monitoring check 2) No quality indicator or metadata 3) The operational Product Details Assessment not made available	1) Uncontrolled storage 2) Only data are stored 3) Data records archiving not managed 4) Preservation information missing 5) Product Details Assessment not made available	No Data/Associated information integrity, authenticity and readability check	1) No representing activities planned 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterization not documented or information not available 3) Post launch calibration & characterization not documented or not available 4) Processing: Additional processing steps not documented	No performance and resolution identifiers available
Level 1 Partially Managed	1) Advertising available 2) Catalogue search available at product level with minimum set of metadata	Basic online services available for data and metadata access	1) Basic schema for metadata data use available and documented standard file format. 2) Data in documented standard file format. 3) No link between non-standard naming conventions used.	1) Already existent mission documentation available and preserved for the long term 2) Link between mission documentation and data records	Product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements assessed to be evenly representative of the satellite measurements, covering a reasonable range of variability of measurements at all data acquisition points 2) Reference Data Quality: single uncertainty estimated for all Validation Results 3) Validation Method: simple uncertainty estimation 4) Validation Results: validation results show good agreement between satellite and reference measurements within uncertainties in most cases.	1) Uncertainty Method: Limited use of GUM approach, analysis, an expanded conversion to measurements by other units 2) Uncertainty Sources: Most important sources of uncertainty included 3) Uncertainty Values: Single uncertainty value provided for subsets of data	1) Basic data quality control and monitoring check 2) Metadata set of quality control procedures documented and available	1) Basic archiving for original data records preservation 2) Assessment of SW preservation 3) Product Details Assessment: Any required information missing	Data Records/Associated information integrity basic check	1) Minor analysis and logs conversion of data records implemented 2) Data Research packaging and/or reformatting 3) Pre-flight calibration & characterization mission some important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose 4) Post launch calibration & characterization covers some important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose 5) Additional processing steps documented. Some important additional processing steps may not be fit for stated purpose.	1) Persistent identifier assignment only for particular data Records 2) Basic landing pages management
Level 2 Managed	1) Detailed catalogue search available at product level 2) Product metadata oriented towards an international standard 3) Data Records Collection and Associated Information available 4) Collection metadata oriented towards an international standard	Simple Access Architecture through metadata packaging/republishing of archived data 1) Data access system oriented towards an international standard 2) Data in well documented standard file format, connectivity having conversion standards	1) Use of non-proprietary international standards including specific interoperability requirements 2) Data access system oriented towards an international standard 3) Data in well documented standard file format, connectivity having conversion standards	1) Documentation produced, additional and well described metadata 2) Link between mission documentation and data records created and managed 3) Metadata available online	1) Metadata available for provenance information 2) Metadata available for provenance information 3) Metadata available for provenance information	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements assessed to be well representative of the satellite measurements, covering a reasonable range of variability of measurements and carried out on a regular basis determined by product performance 2) Reference Data Quality: full uncertainty information, assessed following the GUM and traceable to component reference data 3) Validation Method: assess satellite measurement and reference data w.r.t. their uncertainties 4) Validation Results: show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within uncertainties. Analysis performed independently of satellite mission owner	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty, including breakdown of components and separated as Type A or B uncertainty 2) Uncertainty Sources: All important sources of uncertainty included 3) Uncertainty Values: Total uncertainty per data set provided with base breakdown of key components to error covariance.	1) Quality indicator post processing available 2) Quality control procedures documented and available online	1) Preservation repository certified internally 2) Commonly standard for archiving metadata 3) Product Details Assessment: All required information available, any recommended information missing	1) Data Records/Associated information content integrity check and verification 2) Media readability and accessibility testing	1) Reprocessing for calibration and/or algorithm improvement 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterization covers all important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose 3) Post launch calibration & characterization covers responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance. Calibration transferable to or commonly reference, characterisation meets good practice. 4) Post launch calibration & characterization covers responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance and use appropriate commensurate with the product specifications and carried out regularly across the full range of observational conditions of the product and its variants. 5) Processing: Additional processing steps documented, additional processing steps fit for stated purpose.	1) Persistent identifier assignment for all disseminated data Records 2) Automatic landing page generation and management management of landing pages
Level 3 Fully Managed	1) Product rich metadata fully compliant with an international standard 2) Catalogue accessible to an external operational community agreed upon metadata 3) Data policy on the use of metadata in the catalogues 4) Quality indicator available and accessible 5) Service transition from discovery to access	1) Data and metadata access system fully compliant with an international standard 2) Data policy regarding restrictions of the data, available in the metadata 3) Visualization services allowing user to view images of data as reporting system available 4) Metadata available in the catalogues 5) Quick adoption to new technologies and standards evolution 6) Data and metadata accessible through a free access protocol	1) Accepted and available semantic recording standards for complete interoperability 2) Data and metadata user fully compliant with an international standard 3) Metadata ready data available	1) Standards based metadata for provenance information 2) Link between mission documentation and data records available 3) Automatic metadata available for provenance information 4) Metadata available for provenance information	1) Metadata available for provenance information 2) Metadata available for provenance information 3) Metadata available for provenance information	1) Reference Data Representativeness: Reference measurements independently assessed to be fully representative of the satellite measurements, covering the satellite's full range of measurements and with full coverage of uncertainty and carried out on a regular basis determined by product performance 2) Reference Data Quality: full uncertainty information, assessed following the GUM and traceable to component reference data 3) Validation Method: assess satellite measurement and reference data w.r.t. their error covariance and within those uncertainties 4) Validation Results: show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within uncertainties. Analysis performed independently of satellite mission owner	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty, including breakdown of components and separated as Type A or B uncertainty 2) Uncertainty Sources: All reasonable sources of uncertainty included 3) Uncertainty Values: Uncertainty per data set provided with error covariance information for all appropriate components	1) Data quality control fully compliant with an international standard 2) Quality indicator pre and post processing available in the metadata 3) Quality metadata included	1) Preservation repository publicly certified 2) Product Details Assessment: All required information available, any recommended information missing	1) Automatic Data Records/Associated information content integrity check and verification 2) Data authenticity verifiable internally and by the final user 3) Product Details Assessment: All required and recommended information available	1) Readiness for technology evolution 2) Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be re-used 3) Metadata includes the measurements assessed means uncertainties at component level and their impact on the final product 4) Post launch calibration & characterization covers all responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance. Measurements fully transferable to or commonly reference, characterisation meets good practice. 5) Processing: Additional processing steps fully documented and fit for the art.	1) Persistent identifier assigned for all accessible data Records 2) Metadata includes the identifier for the data 3) Metadata is affected in such a way that it can be accessed and re-used

Figure 6 – Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix

Once the objectives of the ERS preservation and curation activities were defined, the **Preserved Data Set Content** [1] was tailored to generate the detailed list of ERS data, associated information and documentation, software and any other relevant digital object to be preserved for the long term, and to be addressed through valorisation and preservation tasks. One of the most important and critical tasks performed was the **Repatriation** of ERS data from acquisition stations and other facilities all over the world with the objective to generate a Master Data Set for all ERS instruments with the maximum possible temporal and geographical coverage. Repatriation consisted of two main projects:

- The Phase-out project carried out in 2013-15 to repatriate all Low Bit Rate Instruments (LBR) and Synthetic Aperture Radar High Rate (SAR HR) data from ESA Ground Stations and Processing Archiving Centers;
- Repatriation of unique SAR HR data from National and Foreign stations worldwide (see Figure 7), still ongoing.

Figure 7 – Repatriation from National & Foreign Stations

Beside data extracted from modern robotic archives, repatriation activities focused also on heritage media containing potentially unique data, associated Information, software and tools, and hardware (e.g. processing chains, tape readers).

Several thousand legacy media of different kind (e.g. HDDT, DLT, Exabytes, D1), processing and transcription chains hardware and software (e.g. tape readers, servers, CS-DIS chain for data transcription from missions like Landsat, ERS, MOS and MODIS) and relevant documentation were repatriated and located in the EO Heritage Media Archive at ESRIN and in an external warehouse near Rome. A considerable effort was then spent to generate detailed inventories of all repatriated media and hardware in support to gap analysis activities for the identification of unique data still contained on heritage media, and the consequent data re-transcription to fill the identified gaps in the available datasets. Several **Transcription** projects supported by industry (when available) or carried out through the set-up of dedicated transcription chains at ESRIN were started since 2018 and several of them are still ongoing like for example:

- Re-transcription of about 6.5 thousand heritage tapes (HDDTs) containing ERS-1/2 low-rate data for additional gap filling in the master datasets is ongoing at the Matera station in Italy.
- Repatriation from INPE (Brazil) to ESA and re-transcription of 800 HDDT tapes containing unique ERS SAR data acquired at Brazilian stations.
- Transcription at CCMEQ (Canada) of several hundred D1 media containing unique ERS SAR data acquired at Canadian stations and ingestion through a resumed CS-DIS legacy processing environment at ESA/ESRIN to generate the corresponding L0 data products.
- Transcription of few hundred DLT tapes potentially containing unique ERS SAR L0 data repatriated from DLR (Germany) and CONAE (Argentina).

In addition large volumes of ERS SAR data were successfully repatriated from the Alaska Satellite Facility (ASF, USA) and JAXA (acquired at Japanese stations).

Data repatriated, data transcribed and data already available and archived at ESRIN were used as input to a **Consolidation and Certification** process, mostly carried out in 2016-18, which analysed the level of completeness of all ERS instruments datasets to generate “Level-0 Master Datasets” which are devoid of corrupted and duplicated files, and aligned to the same naming convention and file format. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the results of the Level-0 Master Data Set Generation activities for the ERS SAR HR and LBR Instruments data. The consolidation process, which required a huge effort, is still ongoing as new unique data are added to the master data set upon completion of data repatriation and media re-transcription activities.

ERS SAR Master consolidation overall results	2016	2022
Estimated completeness ERS-1 (data coverage vs recorded unavailabilities)	82%	95%
Estimated completeness ERS-2 (data coverage vs recorded unavailabilities)	88%	97%

Figure 8 – ERS SAR Level-0 Master Dataset consolidation

Sensor / Type of product	Estimated completeness % (data coverage vs recorded unavailability's)	Sensor / Type of product	Estimated completeness % (data coverage vs recorded unavailability's)
RA / ERAC	97.82%	RA / ERAC	96.53%
MWR / EMWC	97.83%	MWR / EMWC	97.56%
SWM / EWAC	93.56%	SWM / EWAC	84.62% (*)
WSC / EWIC	96.06%	WSC / EWIC	86.16% (*)
ATSR-1 / RATSr	99.50%	ATSR-2 / EATC-2	91.51%
Telemetry / EGH	96.69%	GOME / EGOC	98.95%
		Telemetry / EGH	82.74%

Figure 9 – ERS LBR Instruments Level-0 Master Datasets consolidation

The following step carried out in 2020-22 consisted in the **Reprocessing** of Level-0 Master Datasets for all LBR Instruments data to generate all planned product types with the latest available Processing Software. New reprocessing campaigns are carried-out when deemed necessary (e.g. to fill identified

gaps, or if a new algorithm/processor becomes available). Different objectives for Data Reprocessing campaigns are identified in the frame of the Heritage Space Programme:

- To improve data quality and/or facilitate data usability and exploitation;
- IPFs/algorithms evolution to align heritage mission dataset to new missions (e.g. Sentinels) and generate long time series for climate change related applications;
- Quality improvement by using new updated auxiliary files;
- Format change to better exploit modern technologies and tools (e.g. Datacubes);
- DOI assignment (after registration) at collection level in the EO-SIP metadata file;
- Compliance with CEOS Analysis Ready Data (ARD) specifications.

A couple of examples of Reprocessing Campaigns carried out in the recent years are described below:

- 4th reprocessing of ATSR-1/2 which includes the harmonisation with Envisat AATSR and Sentinel-3 SLSTR, the Ortho-geolocation, Calibration (incl. 12 micrometers correction), Cloud Masking and uncertainties.

Figure 10 – ERS-1/2 ATSR Reprocessing

- Reprocessing of ERS-1/2 Scatterometer data to Level-1 and Level-2 which includes refined calibration of the 3 backscattering measurements, CMOD5N geophysical forward model, Sea-ice probability and sea-ice flag.

Concerning **Access and Exploitation**, all ERS data products are accessible through the ESA catalogue and dissemination systems [3] on an open and free basis for all users in accordance with ESA Earth Observation Data Policy, together with tools for their exploitation.

Figure 11 – ESA Catalogue

For each available ERS datasets a Landing Page is generated and published on the ESA EO Web Site [3] with the relevant Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

DATA SET SPECIFICATIONS	
Digital Object Identifier (DOI):	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Space Agency, 2017-2021, ERS-1/2 SAR Image Mode Medium Resolution Level 1 Product, IPF version 6.01, https://doi.org/10.5270/ERS-73dhyo 	
Spatial coverage:	82 N, -82 S, -180 W, 180 E
Temporal coverage:	1991-07-27 - 2011-07-04
Date of launch:	1995-04-21, 1991-07-17
Operators:	ESA
Mission status:	completed
Orbit height:	782 to 785 km
Orbit type:	Sun-synchronous
Swath width:	5 km
Current Processor	PF-ERS / Envisat format
Version:	
PROCESSING LEVEL	
level 1	
APPLICABLE TERMS & CONDITIONS	
Utilisation of this data is subject to ESA's Earth Observation Terms and Conditions	

Figure 12 – ERS dataset DOI Specification

ERS data have supported so far over 5000 projects producing some 4000 scientific publications and are maintained accessible and continuously improved in the frame of the Heritage Space Programme to build long-term data series with successor missions including [Envisat](#), ESA's family of [Earth Explorers](#) and the [Copernicus Sentinels](#). Archived data are still widely accessed by users today as they provide a wealth of information which is crucial especially when there is the need to look back in time to monitor changes affecting our Planet (e.g. Climate applications).

Figure 13 – Publications

Figure 14 – ERS Data download in the recent years

Several **Valorisation** activities have and are still being implemented to improve quality of ERS data using new algorithms and processors in alignment with newer missions (e.g. Sentinels). Beside improvement of single datasets, innovative approaches for data valorization are being implemented through the concepts of Fundamental Data Records (FDR) and Analysis Ready Data (CEOS-ARD).

A FDR is a unified and coherent set of single sensor type re-calibrated and inter-satellite calibrated Level1 data. It consists of a consistently reprocessed record of uncertainty-quantified sensor observations that are calibrated to physical units and located in time and space, together with all ancillary and lower-level instrument data used to calibrate and locate the observations and to estimate uncertainty. The FDR concept allows to ensure long-term preservation and valorisation of data, to improve calibrations and uncertainty estimates and reduce multi-mission bias. It facilitates data harmonisation, interoperability and continuity, and is a transparent and fully documented approach supporting new applications and services for a wider user community.

CEOS Analysis Ready Data (CEOS-ARD) [4] are satellite data that have been processed to a minimum set of requirements and organized into a form that allows immediate analysis with a minimum of additional user effort and interoperability both through time and with other datasets. The Analysis Ready Data concept defines and specifies satellite products that have a well-defined format, where common data preparation operations are handled prior to distribution to users. For land surface imagery, this can include operations such as image clipping, geometric correction, and atmospheric correction amongst others. The objective is to reduce the burden of pre-processing on the data user, which can require significant effort, infrastructure, and remote sensing expertise.

Valorisation Projects - FDR

In the frame of the Heritage Space Programme, two main FDR projects have been started addressing **Altimetry and Micro-Wave Radiometer** [4] and **Atmospheric Composition** [5] instruments.

FDR4ALT: the objective of the FDR for Altimetry project is to generate innovative Earth system FDRs (i.e. Level-1 altimeter and radiometer data) and Thematic Products (i.e. level 2P geophysical products). These products will be based on the exploitation of measurements acquired by the altimeter and micro-wave radiometer instruments embarked on-board three ESA heritage remote sensing satellites (ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat). The goal is to serve the different communities involved in long term data exploitation over the different Earth surfaces: ocean, coastal, inland water, ice sheets, sea ice and atmosphere.

Figure 15 – Overview of the FDR4ALT products

The diagrams below display the FDR4ALT product time coverage for the Altimetric Fundamental Data Records (ALT FDR).

Figure 16 – ALT FDR Time Coverage

The diagrams below display the FDR4ALT future product time coverage for the MWR Fundamental Data Records (FDR).

Figure 17 – MWR FDR Time Coverage

The end of the project and release of all products to users is planned for Summer 2023. Follow-on activities to be implemented in the period 2023-25 have been identified and are under assessment/discussion at ESA.

FDR4ATMOS: the objective of the project is to first improve the Envisat SCIAMACHY instrument data quality removing existing biases and degradation, and then to develop a FDR for the GOME & SCIAMACHY instruments. Figure 18 shows the method for **irradiance harmonisation** via transfer function. The end of the project and release of all products to users is planned for Summer 2023. Follow-on activities to be implemented in the period 2023-25 have been identified and are under assessment/discussion at ESA.

Figure 18 – GOME-1 Solar Irradiance

Valorisation Projects - ARD

ERS and Envisat Surface Reflectance, Surface Temperature and Radar products specifications have been assessed against the CEOS Analysis Ready Data (ARD) specifications to identify potential improvement activities to allow data from ESA Heritage Missions to become compliant with CEOS ARD requirements.

Figure 19 – CEOS-ARD Product Family Specifications

Among the several projects started, the **ERS SAR ARD Project** aims at aligning the CEOS ARD products for ERS/Envisat (A)SAR with those of an under development enhanced Sentinel-1 product. The products would be calibrated with RTC (Radiometrically Terrain Corrected), denoised, projected over Copernicus DEM and geolocated allowing as such immediate analysis by users. They would also be based on the same gridding/tiling system and Copernicus 30m DEM to pursue interoperability with Sentinel products, and be cloud-computing compliant (using cloud-optimised STAC, GeoTIFF, VRT, XML). In the flow below the ESA approach for SAR ARD implementation is presented.

Figure 20 – SAR ARD approach for ESA

First results have identified the major corrections which have an impact on ERS data geolocation quality and the potential improvements which can be attained. The completion of the project is foreseen by Q2 2023, with the delivery of the first subset of ERS and Envisat SAR NRB (Normalized Radar Backscatter) ARD products aligned at best to Sentinel-1 corresponding products. In this way it would be possible to easily build long time data series over the same region, being the data processed with similar processing and geographic mapping.

Lessons Learned

The following lessons learned were generated during the ERS activities:

1. Need to create a plan for long term preservation from the Mission Concept Stage / Phase A, to ensure that preservation policies and approaches are applied since the beginning and followed throughout the mission lifetime.
2. The whole process needs to be measured and monitored from data archiving, data migration/transcription and quality control (e.g. following CEOS guidelines [1]).

3. Properly preserve data (more than one copy) and ensure archive technology evolution and media migration.
4. Properly preserve the main information (e.g. start/stop date and time, orbit number, path, etc.) on media labels (if data are available on media) and in digital inventories throughout the entire mission lifetime (particularly for Phases E1 to F2).
5. Preserve other associated information (e.g. station acquisition reports, inventories, etc.) and software in line with internationally recognized Best Practices [1].
6. The Physical Media Archive (if media available) must be a well-controlled environment (humidity, temperature, etc.) to prevent media damage and degradation.
7. Maintain functionality of media reading/transcription chains (hardware and software) including spares for the media available in the archive (and potentially coming from other sources).
8. Ensure Media refreshment (if data kept on media): performed for ESA missions and some TPMs (e.g. HDDTs → DLTs/Exabytes). However some media (e.g. Pegasus tapes containing Landsat data) do not have reader (neither in Europe nor in the US).
9. Keep as long as possible the original media, HW, SW and Associated Information. Several data gaps filled today because the original media and transcription chains were kept and maintained.

References

[1] CEOS WGISS Best Practices and Guidelines -

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